

Product Probability in Quantum Mechanics With One Factor Linked to Maximum Entropy And Information

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In classical statistical mechanics there exists the idea of maximum entropy subject to constraints which is linked to the idea of information. For an equilibrium situation, a given information value is related to the idea that the system does not distinguish products of probabilities (which are functions of information) if information of one plus that of the other equals the given value. For example for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, the maximization of entropy subject to average energy i.e. $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + b \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ leads to a statement of information i.e. $\ln(f(e_i)) = -b e_i$ where $b=1/T$ and $\ln(f(e_i))$ is called information. For equilibrium a given information value say $E=e_i+e_j$ means any e_i, e_j pair's joint probability (product) is fixed i.e. a function of E . (For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein gases, there is a function $g(f(e_i))$ which satisfies the same condition.

In this note, we attempt to consider the idea of information in a quantum bound state. For such a system there is one particle so it cannot collide with other particles to establish equilibrium. It may, however, collide with the potential in a series of impulse hits which on average create $V(x)$ and mimic the idea of an average acceleration i.e. changing kinetic energy from point to point. Breaking $V(x)$ into probabilities linked to impulse hits requires $V(x) = \sum_k V_k G(kx)$ such that $G(kx)$ is invariant over all space and $d/dx G(kx) = k G(kx) c$ where c is a constant. k is the impulse received. A solution is $V_k \exp(ikx)$ which has two factors V_k and $\exp(ikx)$. Each is a type of probability, but with very different natures. $\exp(ikx)$ which is linked to the wavelength shows the nonlocality associated with an impulse k and also that one does not really know k at x which is why this factor is complex. It is this factor, however, which is linked to information in a statistical sense as we argue in the note like e_i in the classical statistical mechanical situation.

The other factor V_k is a probability which is fixed from the constraint $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Analogously, the quantum bound particle is described by a distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. This again has a product probability for each p with factors $a(p)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is related to information (i.e. to maximum entropy) as it combines with $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$. In equilibrium a specific $\exp(ipx)$ is created by various $\exp(ikx) \exp(i(p-k)x)$ terms, but the other factors $V_k a(p-k)$ come into play with $a(p-k)$ being fixed by the constraint: $a(p) p^2/2m + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p)$.

Thus, in quantum mechanics unlike classical statistical mechanics there is a product of probabilities for each p with the imaginary probability $\exp(ipx)$ being linked to information as in the classical statistical case. It is also linked to nonlocality i.e. a wavefunction and the idea that one may not really discern p at x . The second probability factor $a(p)$ may be real and yields information about the probability to find a given p , but with the nature of $\exp(ipx)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$ as a density, it is $a(p)a(p)$ which is the probability $P(p)$ with all information about x removed. $a(p)a(p)$ which depends on the information p is like $f(e_i)$ from classical statistical mechanics in that it is real, but it does not hold at a specific x point and is only fixed through a constraint, not through any maximization of entropy.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained in a number of ways. One may use factorials to count the number of microstates e_i and maximize this subject to constraints. One may maximize Shannon's entropy (also related to a probability) subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ or one may consider a balanced time reversal equation i.e. $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ with $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$.

We examine Shannon's approach here because it is directly linked to information i.e. $\ln(f(e_i))$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. The quantity to be maximized is:

$$-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + b \sum_i e_i f(e_i) \quad ((1)) \text{ where } b \text{ is a Lagrange multiplier}$$

This leads to: $\ln(f(e_i)) = b f(e_i) + 1$ ((2)) where $\ln(f(e_i))$ is called the information and is essentially e_i .

For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, matters are not so simple as one uses an adjusted probability e.g. $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)]$ for the Fermi-Dirac case where $f(e_i)$ is the probability to leave state e_i while $[1-f(e_i)]$ is an unnormalized probability describing the suppression of leaving state e_i . In other words, if e_i is occupied it blocks other particles from scattering into it.

The importance of the information e_i in equilibrium is that if one has say two particle collisions with a total energy of $E = e_i + e_j$, then the product probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ is the same for any e_i, e_j pair which sum to E . This describes a loss of discernment linked to the information quantity. Thus for a two body collision the probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ equals that of the reactants $f(e_k)f(e_l)$ if $e_k + e_l = E$. This ensures conservation of information in these reactions which is equivalent to the physical conservation of energy.

The objective of this note is to attempt to determine the role of information in a quantum bound state.

Information and the Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state differs from a classical mechanical gas in a number of ways. First, there is only one particle and thus equilibrium must be established through hits with the potential $V(x)$. These hits, however, may be modeled as impulses creating a statistical picture, but on average the impulse hits must create $V(x)$. Given the notion of "on average", the impulse hits should be associated with a probability. Thus:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k G(kx) \quad ((3)) \text{ such that } d/dx G(kx) = k b G(kx) \text{ with } b \text{ a constant.}$$

If $G(kx)$ is spatially invariant, a solution is $G(kx) = \exp(ikx)$. This leads to a product probability unlike that of classical statistical mechanics, namely $\sum_k \exp(ikx)$. $\exp(ikx)$ has been determined

independently of V_k . V_k is then found through the constraint $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. In classical statistical mechanics the entire probability $f(e_i)$ is obtained through one approach i.e. maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints. $\exp(ikx)$ is the probability factor which should be linked to maximum entropy and information because of invariance over space, but it is difficult to see this. To make matters clear, one may note that the quantum particle also has a product probability for each p i.e. $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ leading to a probability distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. If one considers the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((4))$$

which represents conservation of average energy at each x , and takes the Fourier transforms of $V(x)$ and $W(x)$, the coefficient of $\exp(ipx)$ is:

$$a(p) \left(\frac{1}{2m} p^2 \right) + \sum_k V(k) a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((5))$$

This is the constraint equation used to find the $a(p)$'s. One may see from the second term on the LHS that $\exp(ipx) = \exp(ikx) \exp(i(p-k)x)$. In other words, with p as information, for a fixed p any combinations k and $p-k$ which add to p have the same product of the second probabilities i.e. $\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(i(p-k)x)$. This is analogous to $\exp(-e_i/T) \exp(-e_j/T)$ with $e_i + e_j = E$. Thus, we argue that the idea of information is present in both the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas where it is e_i , and in the quantum bound state where it is p , but the quantum case differs because it has product probabilities. Information which is linked to equilibrium is present because different $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ probabilities are colliding with $\exp(ikx)$ probabilities from the potential in an impulse transfer way, but the first probabilities still come into the picture and $a(p)$ must be solved from the constraint equation ((5)).

Consideration of $a(p)$

$a(p)$ is an unusual probability (first factor probability) because it is not obtained through a statistical process i.e. maximization of entropy or invariance in space etc. It is calculated through a constraint. $\exp(ipx)$, the second probability factor represents maximum entropy - information type statistics of the problem, but it also describes nonlocality. $\exp(ipx)$ is complex because one may not describe a probability of finding p at x because each p is continuously changing at x . It is only over a wavelength (proportional to $1/p$) that p is defined. Different p 's have different wavelengths, so various p 's are distinguished over all space. Using $W^*(x)W(x)$ as $P(x)$ and integrating $\int dx P(x)$ leads to $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$. Thus $a^*(p)a(p)$ is a probability describing $P(p)$, but is completely detached from x . In a certain sense $a^*(p)a(p)$ is like $f(e_i)$ from classical statistical mechanics in what it represents, but is obtained in a completely different manner. $f(e_i)$ is obtained by the maximization of entropy with the use of a constraint, while $a(p)$ is simply obtained through a constraint assuming that there is a second probability factor of the form $\exp(ipx)$ which reflects maximum entropy or information.

One may ask whether it is possible that the $a^*(p)a(p)$ probability reflects statistical properties related to information. It has been argued that for equilibrium, for a given value of information

product probabilities, which are functions of information, have a fixed value if information of one plus information of the other yields the given value. There is a special case for which this may be applied to $a^*(p)a(p)$. First, p is the information for the second factor $\exp(ipx)$, but $a^*(p)a(p)$ is real and so a different variable for information is required. An alternative is to consider the information from the classical statistical mechanical MB gas i.e. $pp/2m$. If $a(p) = \exp(-b pp/2m)$ then $a^*(p)a(p)$ is of the same form. This, however, is $\exp(-ei/T)$ where $ei=pp/2m$ as in classical statistical mechanics. In such a case, $a(p)a(p)$ behaves as an equilibrium result based on information, but only for this special case. The situation for which $a(p) = \exp(-bpp/2m)$ is that of the ground state of a harmonic oscillator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to take the idea of information from classical statistical mechanical equilibrium (e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas for which it is ei) and find an analogous information for a quantum bound state. We argue that for a bound state a product probability holds. A quantum bound state has only one particle which must stochastically interact with a potential. In other words the potential represents impulse hits linked to probability because on average it becomes $V(x)$. If one wishes to have spatial invariance and the average of impulses k times probability equal $-d/dx V(x)$ then $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ is a solution. In other words there is a product probability with V_k being the first probability and $\exp(ikx)$ the second. $\exp(ikx)$ is forced through spatial invariance and impulse hits and we argue that it is linked to maximum entropy in the sense that it is spatially invariant. It also represents nonlocality and leads to $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms for the quantum particle if one wishes to have an impulse of k change p to $p+k$ with same probability structure i.e. $\exp(ipx) \exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$. One may already see the beginnings of p as information because for a given p i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ results from any combination $\exp(ikx)\exp(i(p-k)x)$. This is analogous to $\exp(-ei/T)$ in classical statistical mechanics. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is only the second probability factor. There is still the first probability factor $a(p)$ which must be found through a constraint.

Thus, classical statistical mechanics (MB gas) and a quantum bound state both have information in equilibrium, but it is ei for the MB gas and p for the quantum bound particle. Furthermore, there is a real probability $f(ei)$ for an MB gas which exists at each x and is obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to an energy constraint.

For the quantum case, a particle receives impulse hits from a potential $V(x)$ with these leading to $V(x)$ on average. Thus, $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ is a solution satisfying this condition and leads to the $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ terms for the bound particle such that upon receiving an impulse hit, its probability changes according to: $a(p)\exp(ipx)V_k \exp(ikx)$. It is the second term which behave according to the information equilibrium condition of classical statistical mechanics i.e. for a given $\exp(ipx)$ any pair $\exp(ikx)$, $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ yields the same product probability. There is nevertheless the first probability factor $a(p)$ which must be calculated through a constraint condition. In other words, it does not follow the information equilibrium (except for the special case of the quantum ground state of an oscillator with the information $pp/2m$ for $a(p)$ and p for $\exp(ipx)$).

Thus information equilibrium conditions which hold in classical statistical mechanics [e.g. MB gas: $e_i + e_j = E$ means $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(E)$] hold for one factor of the quantum probability namely $\exp(ipx)$ while the second $a(p)$ is fixed through a constraint.